

An analytical form to fit both fine and coarse grained quartz OSL–SAR dose response curves

John L. Lawless^a, A. Timar-Gabor^b

^a*Redwood Scientific, Pacifica, California, USA*

^b*Interdisciplinary Research Institute on Bio-Nano-Science, Babeş-Bolyai University, Cluj-Napoca, Romania, and Faculty of Environmental Sciences and Engineering, Babeş-Bolyai University, Cluj-Napoca, Romania*

Abstract

We address two issues: (a) the choice of suitable analytic forms for curve fitting quartz OSL–SAR dose response data and (b) possible physical interpretations of the difference between fine (4–11 μm) and coarse (63–90 μm) grain samples. We start with a phenomenological model with three levels: an OSL–active trap, a deep trap, and a radiative center. This model yields a simple analytic form for the dose response under the optically stimulated luminescence–single-aliquot regenerative dose (OSL–SAR) protocol. By comparing with experimental data from nine quartz samples, we show that this form provides excellent agreement and may, in some cases, be better than the commonly–used double–saturating–exponential form despite this form having fewer adjustable constants. Further, because this analytic form is derived from a model, physical parameters can be inferred from the curve fits. In particular, concentrations for the OSL–active and deep electron traps can be computed and the variation in concentrations of these traps between samples is discussed. Within this model, the difference between fine and coarse grain samples is consistent with the OSL–active trap being a surface trap as opposed to a volume trap.

Keywords: Quartz, Grain size, Optically–stimulated luminescence (OSL), Dose response, Saturation characteristics

1. Introduction

This mss addresses two issues. The first is the choice of suitable analytic forms for curve-fitting quartz OSL-SAR dose-response data. The second is the development of a possible explanation for the difference between the dose-response curves of fine (4–11 μm) and coarse (63–90 μm) grains of quartz. Both of these issues will be addressed with a simple three-level phenomenological model.

Under the OSL-SAR method, the laboratory-measured dose response must be curve fit and inaccuracy of this curve fit can limit the accuracy of the dose determination. The double-saturating-exponential (DSE) form has been widely and successfully used for this curve-fitting. (Murray et al., 2007; Pawley et al., 2010; Lowick et al., 2010; Timar-Gabor et al., 2012) Pagonis et al. (2020) have suggested the use of a one-trap one-center (OTOR) model as an alternative. In furtherance of that suggestion, we develop an extended OTOR model here, denoted OTORX, which we compare with the experimental data of Timar-Gabor et al. (2012, 2017). We find that many—not all but many—of the quartz samples show a good fit to this model.

A benefit of curve-fitting of the dose-response to a physically-based model is that it enables physical interpretation of the observed behavior. This model allows more than one physical interpretation and we will consider different interpretations and what they imply about the trap concentrations and the relative importance of key rate constants.

There are many features of quartz thermoluminescence and OSL that can only be understood using more comprehensive models. (Bailey, 2001, 2004; Adamiec et al., 2006; Kijek and Chruścińska, 2016; Peng et al., 2022) For this mss, our interest is restricted to dose response curves. While there are some observed dose response curves that show complexity not included in our simple model, there were a very large number that did fit the simple model very well. These good fits were achieved despite the simple model having fewer adjustable constants than competing empirical formulas.

It is observed that OSL from aliquots made of fine quartz particles have distinctly different dose response curves than aliquots of coarse quartz particles. This is curious because one would expect that the intrinsic properties of the material, such as rate constants and trap and center concentrations, to be unaffected by extrinsic grain dimensions. Our simple model implies that the

difference between the fine and coarse grain particles is in the concentration of the fast-OSL trap.

It is known that some traps exist in the volume of a material and others on the surface or other interfaces.(Goetzberger et al., 1976; Hölzl et al., 1979; Lüth, 2001; Ibach, 2006) Surfaces and interfaces can be rich with dangling bonds, back bonds, adsorbed atoms, and surfaces steps, all of which can lead to the creation of traps and centers. This applies not just to outside surfaces but also to interior interfaces such as at pores or voids. Surface traps and centers have practical importance in semiconductor devices such as magnetodiodes.(Heremans, 1993; Popovic et al., 1984) For quartz in particular, there is strong evidence that a number of different TL/OSL-active traps and centers are located on surfaces. Giordano et al. (2007), for example, performed quantum mechanical calculations which predicted that both nonbridging oxygen centers and silicon dangling bonds would create thermally-stable electron traps on silica surfaces. Using electron spin resonance, Timar-Gabor (2018) experimentally observed the presence of E'-centers and peroxy centers on the surface or in internal voids/cracks or other damaged areas of sedimentary quartz. Skuja et al. (2020) experimentally observed photoluminescence from oxygen dangling bonds on the surfaces of crystalline SiO₂.

Fine grains, of course, have a higher surface-to-volume ratio than coarse grains and, if the fast-OSL trap was an interface trap, this would explain the difference between dose response curves for fine *vs.* coarse grains. We will show that this is consistent with experimentally observed scaling laws for dose response *vs.* grain size.

In the next section, the OTORX model is developed. In Sec. (3), this model is applied to fit the OSL-SAR dose response curves of nine silica samples. Within the limits of the OTORX, model the physical significance of the curve fit parameters are explored and a possible physical explanation of the difference between fine and coarse silica grains is presented. Lastly, in Sec. (4), summary and conclusions are presented.

2. Phenomenological model

We will use a simple model consisting of two electron traps and one radiative recombination center as shown in Fig. 1. In this section, we present the governing equations and their solution. Since the solution is analytic, it is

Figure 1: Energy level diagram of the model with an active trap N , a disconnected trap N_D , and a hole recombination center M . During irradiation, electron–hole pairs are created with rate X . During OSL, electrons freed from trap N with rate λ .

suitable for curve–fitting against experimental data as will be demonstrated in Sec. (3).

In this model, The OSL–active electron trap has a total (filled plus empty) concentration of N (cm^{-3}) and the concentration of occupied traps of n (cm^{-3}). The hole–type recombination center is assumed to be radiative with a total (filled plus empty) concentration of M (cm^{-3}) with a concentration of occupied centers being m (cm^{-3}). Lastly, we include a deep trap with total concentration N_D and a concentration of occupied traps of n_D . In the notation of Bailey (2001), trap N can be identified with ‘Level 3 (OSL_F),’ center M with ‘Level 8 (L–center),’ and N_D with ‘Level 5 (Deep).’¹

X is the rate of production of electron–hole pairs per unit volume during irradiation. For generality, we will allow X to vary with time: $X = X(t)$. In theoretical work, the dose is often measured as the integral of X over time which has units of electron–hole pairs created per unit volume. In experimental work, dose is typically measured in Grays which has units of energy deposited per unit mass: $1 \text{ Gy} = 1 \text{ J/kg}$. To convert between the two, we need to know W which is the average energy in Joules deposited per

¹Note that Bailey (2004) uses a different level numbering scheme than Bailey (2001).

electron–hole pair created, and ρ the mass density, in kg/m^3 , of the material. Thus, the total dose, in Grays, that the material experiences over time t is:

$$D = \frac{W}{\rho} \int_0^t X(t') dt' \quad (1)$$

where t' is a variable of integration. W is determined experimentally and is known for a variety of materials. (Lawless et al., 2022; Attix, 2004; Arshak and Korostynska, 2006; Ryan, 1973; Scholze et al., 1998; Alig and Bloom, 1975; Klein, 1968; Goldstein, 1965; Barnett et al., 2013) The value for pure silica is $W=17 \text{ eV}=2.7 \times 10^{-18} \text{ J}$. For the current work, we will assume that the density of quartz is $\rho=2,650 \text{ kg}/\text{m}^3$.

We will assume that, immediately after the silica was created, the traps and center are all empty:

$$n = N_D = m = 0 \quad (2)$$

We are interested in measurements of burial dose. As is usual, we will assume that the burial is preceded by a large geological dose (Pagonis et al., 2008), which fills trap N_D , and exposure to light, which empties n . Thus, at the start of the last burial, the trap populations are:

$$n = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad n_D = m = N_D \quad (3)$$

Since the deep trap is neither OSL–active nor thermally unstable at temperatures used during the SAR procedure, it remains filled during SAR. The corresponding phenomenological equations for irradiation are:

$$\frac{dn}{dt} = A_n(N - n)n_c \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{dn_D}{dt} = 0 \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{dn_c}{dt} = X - A_n(N - n)n_c - A_m m n_c \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{dm}{dt} = B(M - m)n_v - A_m m n_c \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{dn_v}{dt} = X - B(M - m)n_v \quad (8)$$

where X (cm^{-3}/s) is the production rate of electron–hole pairs due to irradiation and A_m (cm^3/s) is the rate constant for recombination of free electrons

with the center. A_n (cm^3/s) is the rate constant for trapping of free electrons in the trap N . B (cm^3/s) is the rate constant for trapping of free holes in the center.

The lifetimes of free electrons, n_c , and free holes, n_v , are generally short compared to the time scale at which irradiation occurs. This allows the quasi-steady approximation to be applied. The details are in Appendix A where an analytical solution is developed that gives the trap population n_1 as a function of dose, D :

$$n = N F(D/D_{63\%}, Q) \quad (9)$$

where the function F is defined by:

$$F(d, Q) \equiv \begin{cases} 1 + \frac{1}{Q} \mathcal{W}(-Q \exp(-(1 - \frac{e-1}{e}Q)d - Q)) & \text{for } Q \neq 0 \\ 1 - \exp(-d) & \text{for } Q = 0 \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

where $e \approx 2.718$ is the base of the natural logarithm, \mathcal{W} is the Wright Omega function², and Q is an abbreviation for:

$$Q = \frac{A_m - A_n}{A_m} \frac{N}{N + N_D} \quad (11)$$

$D_{63\%}$ is a characteristic dose defined by:

$$D_{63\%} \equiv \frac{W}{\rho} \frac{A_m}{A_n} (N + N_D) \left[1 - \frac{e-1}{e} Q \right] \quad (12)$$

An examination of the equations shows that $D_{63\%}$ is the dose at which the trap occupation after irradiation, n , is $\frac{e-1}{e} \approx 63\%$ of the saturated value, N .

The above examines the material response to irradiation. The OSL step is simpler. OSL empties the trap n and, in this simple model, the only place for the freed electrons to go is into the radiative center. Thus, the integrated OSL intensity, defined as photons released per unit volume of material, is just the trap concentration after irradiation:

$$I = n \quad (13)$$

²The Wright Omega function is supported by major mathematics packages. For SciPy, for example, it is found under `scipy.special.wrightomega`

It follows that the integrated intensity at saturation, I_{sat} , is N . Combining Eq. (9) with Eq. (13), we have the OSL intensity profile as a function of dose:

$$\frac{I}{I_{\text{sat}}} = F(D/D_{63\%}, Q) \quad (14)$$

where F was defined in Eq. (10).

The parameter Q controls the shape of the material's dose response. The possible shapes of the dose response curves are shown in Fig. 2. Since A_m , A_n , N , and N_D are all nonnegative numbers, it is clear from Eq. (11) that the range of possible values for the parameter Q is:

$$-\infty < Q \leq 1 \quad (15)$$

We can consider three limiting cases for Q :

1. $Q \rightarrow -\infty$: This happens when the trapping rate constant A_n is much larger than the recombination rate constant A_m : $A_n \gg A_m$. In this case, the dose response curve is linear up to saturation. The curve in Fig. 2 for $Q = -100$ illustrates this.
2. $Q = 0$: In this case, as shown in Eq. (9), the dose response curve is the familiar single saturating exponential. A curve computed with $Q=0$ is shown in Fig. 2. $Q = 0$ occurs either when $A_n = A_m$ or the concentration of the deep trap is large: $N_D/N \rightarrow \infty$.
3. $Q = 1$: This case indicates strong recombination, $A_m \gg A_n$ and a very low concentration of the deep trap: $N_D/N \rightarrow 0$. This dose response curve is strongly sublinear, as shown in the $Q=1$ curve in Fig. 2. This sublinearity is caused by competition between the recombination center and the electron trap. (Lawless et al., 2009)

The single-aliquot regenerative-dose procedure uses several steps. (Murray and Wintle, 2003; Wintle and Murray, 2006) As it applies to our simple model, which includes just a single fast-OSL trap, n , and no other OSL-active traps, the key points to this procedure are that before each radiation dose applied, the OSL-active trap n is emptied. After each radiation dose, the OSL signal is measured. The applied doses alternate between a dose of varying magnitude, called a *laboratory* dose, and a fixed *test* dose. The integrated OSL after the laboratory dose is called L_x and the integrated OSL after the test dose is called T_x . For each laboratory dose, the normalized

Figure 2: The OSL intensity, normalized by the intensity at saturation is plotted against applied dose, normalized by the dose at 63% of saturation for various values of parameter Q .

luminescence, L_x/T_x is reported. For the experiments of Timar-Gabor et al. (2012), the test is 17 Gy. Thus:

$$L_x/T_x = \frac{F(D/D_{63\%}, Q)}{F(17\text{Gy}/D_{63\%}, Q)} \quad (16)$$

Thus, in our model, the OSL–SAR response should depend on only two parameters: $D_{63\%}$ which is a measure of the saturation dose and Q which measures the relative importance of trapping *vs.* recombination. After comparing the Eq. (16) with experimental data, it was found that a small correction was needed. As an artifact of the SAR procedure, a laboratory dose typically produces larger luminescence than a test dose even if both doses have the same magnitude. To accommodate this bias, a factor c was added:

$$L_x/T_x = c \frac{F(D/D_{63\%}, Q)}{F(17\text{Gy}/D_{63\%}, Q)} \quad (17)$$

While c varies from one material to the next, it was typically within a several per cent of one. The cause of this correction is outside the scope of this model.

In sum, a simple model has been created with one recombination center, one OSL–active trap, and one deep trap which is assumed to have been filled during the geological dose. As this is an extension of the OTOR model, we will denote it OTORX. With this model, OSL–SAR luminescence data can be fit with three parameters: $D_{63\%}$ which is the dose at 63% of saturation, Q which measures the relative importance of trapping and recombination, and c whose value is close to one. The final form of this model for OSL–SAR is Eq. (17) where the function F was defined in Eq. (10).

3. Results

The theory of the previous section will be compared against nine of the quartz samples as were measured by Timar et al. (2010); Timar-Gabor et al. (2011, 2012). We will start by examining the dose response curve of a particular sample, MV10, in detail. We will find that, in addition to having fewer adjustable constants, the OTORX model gives a better fit to MV10 than the double–saturating–exponential (DSE) formula. This is followed by an examination of fits to the dose response curves for eight more samples, four fine and four coarse grained. All four possibilities of N and N_D being

either volume or surface traps will be considered. We will find that, when both traps are assumed to be surface traps, the agreement between theory and experiment is excellent both for the dose response curves and for the scaling those curves with grain size.

3.1. Sample MV10

As an example, consider sample MV10 from the Mircea Vodă in south-eastern Romania. (Timar-Gabor et al., 2012) The MV10 experimental data, shown with error bars, is compared against the OTORX best fit (solid line) in Fig. 3a. The parameters of the best fit are $Q = 0.90$, $D_{63\%} = 823$ Gy, and $c = 1.09$. That Q is close to one indicates that recombination, A_m , is strong compared with trapping, A_n . RMS error for this fit is 2.3%. As this is about the same magnitude as the statistical error in the experiments, any better fit would likely not have physical significance.

To assess the degree to which Q can be determined accurately, an additional series of curve fits to the MV10 data were performed holding Q fixed while optimizing $D_{63\%}$ and c . The resulting RMS error for each Q value is shown in Fig. 3b. It shows that values over the range $0.89 < Q < 0.91$ all provide fits with RMS errors that remain close to the experimental statistical error.

Also, for comparison, the double-saturating-exponential (DSE) fit to the MV10 data (dashed line) is shown in Fig. 3a. This fit has an RMS error of 4.9%, over double that of the OTORX fit. Note that the DSE fit uses five adjustable constants while the OTORX fit uses merely three.

Suppose, hypothetically, that we had perfect model equations. Then, if a series of experiments are performed, the standard deviation between the model and the experiment would fluctuate from experiment to experiment but, on average, be the same as the experiment's statistical errors. This is what we observe with the OTORX fit to the MV10: the RMS error is the same as the expected statistical noise. While the OTORX is not perfect, it is close enough to the experiment that we cannot tell the difference between it and a better model without additional experimental data.

In sum, the fit of the OTORX model to MV10 data is excellent. The RMS error between the OTORX model and the data is half that of the DSE fit.

Figure 3: (a) The OSL–SAR luminescence, L_x/T_x , is plotted against laboratory dose. The experimental data points are shown with error bars of ± 2 standard deviation. The solid line shows the best fit from the OTORX model. Also shown is the best fit using double–saturating–exponential (dashed line, Timar-Gabor et al. (2012)). (b) For various values of Q , the RMS error is computed holding Q constant but optimizing $D_{63\%}$ and c and the resulting RMS error is then plotted against Q .

Table 1: The dose response curves for eight samples were fitted to the analytical model, Eq. (17), and the curve fit parameters and fit accuracy are shown below. The samples are from four locations, with one fine and one coarse sample from each location. As per the models proposed in Sec. (3.2) and Sec. (3.3), the value of Q is constrained to be the same for fine and coarse samples from the same location. The column labeled ‘RMS Error’ refers to the root-mean-square error in the fitted dose response curve.

Material	Q	Fine			Coarse		
		$D_{63\%}$ (Gy)	c	RMS Error (%)	$D_{63\%}$ (Gy)	c	RMS Error (%)
M#6#	0.732	462	1.023	1.9	181	1.254	0.4
XF 153 A	0.806	624	1.013	3.3	168	1.140	2.6
CST inf	0.791	627	1.039	2.7	200	1.106	1.9
MST 19	0.836	800	1.076	2.2	296	1.105	2.7

3.2. Fine vs. coarse under strict OTOR model ($N_D = 0$)

We will now consider eight more samples, four fine-grained and four-coarse grained. Instead of treating the OTORX equation as simple curve fitting, we will apply some physical considerations and restrict the range of allowed parameters. We start by applying a strict OTOR model, meaning that there are no deep traps: $N_D=0$. In this case, Q simplifies to $Q = 1 - A_n/A_m$. Assuming that the fine and coarse samples from the same location have the same composition and structure, and thus the same set traps and centers, then it is expected that the rate constants A_n and A_m will be unchanged. In this case, Q should be the same for both fine and coarse samples. Thus, for each of four source locations, we curve fit the fine and coarse data from that location, optimizing $D_{63\%}$ and c for each sample while constraining Q to be the same for both. The resulting fits are shown in Fig. 4 and Table 1. The observed values of Q are in the range $0.73 < Q < 0.84$ while the characteristic dose $D_{63\%}$ is observed to vary greatly between fine samples, for which $462 < D_{63\%} \leq 800$ is observed, and the coarse samples, for which $168 \leq D_{63\%} \leq 296$ is observed.

The designation for each sample is the laboratory code used by Timar-Gabor et al. (2012, 2017). MST refers to the Mostistea section of the Romanian plain. CST refers to samples taken from the Costinești section near the Black Sea shore. XF comes from the Xifeng section in the Chinese loess plateau. M#6 is quartz extracted from a carbonate eolianite from Eivissa.

Figure 4: The OSL-SAR dose response curves are shown on a log-log plot for fine (black, solid) and coarse (gray, dashed) samples from four locations. The x-axis shows applied dose in Grays and the y-axis shows OSL intensity at that dose divided by the intensity of a 17 Gy test dose.

Table 2: The material parameters derived from the curve fits to samples as shown in Fig. 2 and Table 1 under the assumed strict one-trap one-center model ($N_D = 0$).

Material	A_n/A_m	N (fine)	N (coarse)
M#6#	0.27	2.2×10^{17}	8.8×10^{16}
XF 153 A	0.19	2.4×10^{17}	6.5×10^{16}
CST inf	0.21	2.5×10^{17}	8.1×10^{16}
MST 19	0.16	2.7×10^{17}	1×10^{17}

Using the strict OTOR model, the observed Q and $D_{63\%}$ values can be converted to values for more fundamental physical properties. As noted above, under the strict OTOR model ($N_D = 0$), Q simplifies to $Q = 1 - A_n/A_m$. Solving Eq. (11) and Eq. (12) for A_n/A_m and N yields:³

$$A_n/A_m = 1 - Q \quad (18)$$

$$N = \frac{1 - Q}{1 - \frac{e-1}{e}Q} \frac{D_{63\%}}{W/\rho} \quad (19)$$

Consequently, knowing both Q and $D_{63\%}$ from Table 1, we can solve for the ratio of the trapping to recombination rate constants, A_n/A_m and for the total trap population N . These are shown in Table 2. From the table, the recombination rate coefficient A_m is found to be four to six times larger than the trapping rate coefficient A_n which is consistent with the experimentally observed sublinear dose response. From this model, the trap concentration N in the fine samples appears as roughly three times larger than the trap concentration N in coarse samples.

In sum, the strong and consistent difference in dose response curves between fine and coarse samples appears to be explained by a higher trap concentration N in the fine samples. If traps were uniformly distributed through the volume of the silica, it would be hard to explain why fine samples should have a higher number of traps per unit volume than coarse samples. An alternative is that the traps are not located in the volume of the silica but rather

³As long as A_n and A_m are large enough that the quasi-steady approximation applies, the dose response curve will depend only on their ratio, not their absolute values. If we wanted to determine their individual values, a different type of experiment would be required.

at the surfaces (or interfaces) of silica. The existence of surface traps on silica has long been recognized. (Goetzberger et al., 1976; Hölzl et al., 1979; Lüth, 2001; Ibach, 2006; Giordano et al., 2007; Timar-Gabor, 2018; Skuja et al., 2020) If silica’s fast-OSL traps were surface traps, then this would explain the increase in N for smaller grains.

The scaling of the density of surface traps with grain size can be subtle. If the grains are solid spheres with smooth surfaces but varying diameters, then the ratio of surface area S to volume V scales as:

$$\frac{S}{V} \sim \phi^{-1} \quad (20)$$

where ϕ is the grain diameter. If the surface is rough, then the scaling becomes:

$$\frac{S}{V} \sim \phi^{D_F-3} \quad (21)$$

where D_F is a fractal dimension of the surface. For the smooth sphere, $D_F = 2$. For a grain with a very rough surface or with many deep cracks or pores, D_F can approach 3. The scaling of saturation dose with grain size has been studied by Timar-Gabor et al. (2017) with the result that the saturation dose scaled with $\phi^{-1/2}$. This is consistent with the traps being surface or interface traps and the grain’s surface having a fractal dimension of $D_F = 2.5$.

Another feature of Table 2 that requires discussion is the ratio A_n/A_m . While the concentrations of traps and centers may vary widely from one sample to another, depending on relative concentrations of impurities and geological history, the rate constants, by contrast, are intrinsic properties of their respective crystal defects. While they may be affected by their local environment in the crystal, no significant change in the rate constant for a particular trap or center is expected. (Bailey, 2004) Thus, the variation in A_n/A_m between samples in Table 2 could be considered a problem with the strict OTOR model. The improved model in the next section eliminates this problem.

3.3. *Fine vs. coarse under OTORX model with both N and N_D as surface traps*

We will apply the more general OTORX model of Sec. (2), with nonzero N_D , to the same eight samples. In this model, we can assume that all quartz

samples, regardless of origin, have the same rate constant A_n and A_m and consequently the same ratio A_n/A_m , eliminating the issue identified with the strict OTOR model. Further, we will assume in this section that N_D is, like N , a surface trap and, thus, for samples from the same location, N_D will increase in the same proportion as N between coarse and fine grains. Under these assumptions, an examination of Eq. (11) shows that Q will have the same value for coarse and fine samples from a single location but can vary one location to the next. This matches the conditions under which Table 1 was computed. We cannot tell from this model what the value of A_n/A_m should be but, from Eq. (11), we can tell that

$$A_n/A_m \leq 1 - Q \quad \text{if } Q > 0 \quad (22)$$

Since our observed Q values are positive and Q values of up to 0.9 have been observed, this restricts the ratio of rate constants to $A_n/A_m \leq 0.1$. For purposes of illustration, we will pick $A_n/A_m = 0.08$. Using the values of Q and $D_{63\%}$ from Table 1 and the assumed value of A_n/A_m , we can solve Eq. (11) and Eq. (12) for N and N_D as:

$$N = \frac{A_n/A_m}{1 - A_n/A_m} \frac{Q}{1 - \frac{e-1}{e}Q} \frac{D_{63\%}}{W/\rho} \quad (23)$$

$$N_D = \frac{A_n/A_m}{1 - A_n/A_m} \frac{1 - A_n/A_m - Q}{1 - \frac{e-1}{e}Q} \frac{D_{63\%}}{W/\rho} \quad (24)$$

This leads to the trap concentration shown in Table 3 for our eight materials. Under these assumptions, fast-OSL trap concentration N across these four locations varies over a factor of two while the deep trap concentration N_D varies by somewhat less.

In sum, this both-surface-trap assumption avoids the problems with the physical constants of the strict-OTOR model. Two features of this case are that (1) the saturation dose $D_{63\%}$ may vary from sample to sample, but (2) the low-dose shape parameter Q is constrained to be the same for both fine and coarse samples from the same location. This case provides excellent fits to the experimental data.

3.4. Fine vs. coarse under OTORX model under other assumptions

The previous section considered the case of both the fast-OSL trap N and the deep trap N_D being surface traps. Under this assumption, the shape

Table 3: The rate constant and trap population are shown for fine and coarse grained samples from four locations under the OTORX model with both N and N_D treated as surface traps (see text for details). These are the results of applying Eq. (23) and Eq. (24) to the values shown in Table 1. The RMS errors for these fits are shown in Table 1.

Material	A_n/A_m	Fine		Coarse	
		N (cm ⁻³)	N_D (cm ⁻³)	N (cm ⁻³)	N_D (cm ⁻³)
M#6#	0.08	5.3×10^{16}	1.4×10^{16}	2.1×10^{16}	5.4×10^{15}
XF 153 A	0.08	8.7×10^{16}	1.2×10^{16}	2.3×10^{16}	3.3×10^{15}
CST inf	0.08	8.4×10^{16}	1.4×10^{16}	2.7×10^{16}	4.3×10^{15}
MST 19	0.08	1.2×10^{17}	1.2×10^{16}	4.4×10^{16}	4.5×10^{15}

factor Q is the same for fine and coarse grains but the saturation dose $D_{63\%}$ is much larger for fine grains than coarse ones. This led to very good agreement with experimental data. In this section, we will consider the other three possible combinations of N and N_D being surface or volume traps.

Let us first consider the case that both N and N_D are volume traps. This means, under our model, that both the quantities N and N_D are intrinsic properties and unaffected by extrinsic dimensions of the grain. Thus, for samples from the same source, these concentrations are constrained to be the same for fine and coarse samples. From Eq. (11) and Eq. (12), this means that those fine and coarse samples must have the same Q and $D_{63\%}$. This restriction on Q is the same as for the both-surface-trap assumption. The constraint on $D_{63\%}$ is, however, important: experimental data shows $D_{63\%}$ for fine samples is typically three times larger than for coarse samples. Consequently, the fit to experiment for this case is poor. This is shown in Fig. 5 where the RMS errors of the fit assuming both traps are volume traps are shown for each of eight quartz samples. The circles show the RMS errors for the both-volume-trap model and these errors are much larger than for the both-surface-trap model (diamond symbols).

As the next case, we will keep N as a volume trap but treat N_D as a surface trap. Thus, N_D is expected to be larger for fine samples than coarse ones. This means, from Eq. (11) and Eq. (12), that Q and $D_{63\%}$ may differ between fine and coarse grains, and this gives the possibility of better fits to experiment than the case with both being volume traps. The ability to fit experiment, though, is limited as we can see from combining Eq. (11) and

Figure 5: The RMS accuracy of the fits of the model to experiment are shown for fine and coarse grains of each of the four materials. Four different assumptions are used: (a) both N and N_D are surface traps (diamonds), (b) both N and N_D are volume traps (circles), (c) N is a surface trap while N_D is a volume trap (triangles), and (d) N is a volume trap while N_D is a surface trap (inverted triangles). The solid lines are merely guides for the eye.

Eq. (12):

$$D_{63\%} = \frac{W}{\rho} \frac{1 - A_n/A_m}{A_n/A_m} \frac{1 - \frac{e-1}{e} Q}{Q} N \quad (25)$$

Here, W , ρ , A_n , and A_m are all material constants and $e = 2.718$. Further, with N a volume trap, N must be the same for both fine and coarse samples. This leaves Q as the only variable on the right-hand-side of Eq. (25) that can change between fine and coarse samples from the same location. This means that Q and $D_{63\%}$ cannot be adjusted independently. Eq. (25) shows that, under this case, if $D_{63\%}$ is larger in fine samples, then Q must be smaller. As can be seen in Fig. 5, this case (denoted by triangles) yields a better fit to experiment than the both-volume-trap case but not as good as the both-surface-trap case.

Lastly, we will consider the case of fast-OSL trap N being a volume trap while deep trap N_D is a surface trap. In this case, N is an intrinsic property and, under our model, must be the same for fine and coarse grains from the same location. We can again rearrange Eq. (11) and Eq. (12) but this time to eliminate the variable N in favor of N_D :

$$D_{63\%} = \frac{W}{\rho} \frac{1 - A_n/A_m}{A_n/A_m} \frac{1 - \frac{e-1}{e} Q}{1 - A_n/A_m - Q} N_D \quad (26)$$

Here, W , ρ , A_n , and A_m are again material constants, $e=2.1718$, and N_D , as a volume trap, is constrained to be the same for fine and coarse grains. Eq. (26) shows that, for this case also, $D_{63\%}$ and Q are not independent. A difference between Eq. (25) and Eq. (26) is that $1 - A_n/A_m - Q$ can be a number close to zero and this means that $D_{63\%}$ in Eq. (26) can be very sensitive to small changes in Q . As a result, the large difference in $D_{63\%}$ between fine and coarse grains can be accommodated by smaller changes in Q . As can be seen in Fig. 5, this results in a better fit to experiment than the other cases involving volume traps but still not as good as the both-surface-trap case.

In sum, this section considered three possible cases, each involving one or more traps being volume traps. For fine and coarse grains from the same location, all three cases placed constraints on $D_{63\%}$ to either be the same for both (the both-volume-trap case) or to differ only if Q also differed. This resulted in poorer fits to experiment than the both-surface-trap case discussed in the previous section.

4. Summary

To estimate the burial dose accurately under the OSL–SAR protocol, it is important to have an accurate curve fit to the dose response curve. We have shown that a simple phenomenological model yields an analytical expression that closely fits many silica samples. The model also offers possible explanations for the physical origin of the differences in dose response curves.

The analytical expression has three constants: Q , $D_{63\%}$, and c . Q affects the sublinearity of the dose response. For the sedimentary quartz samples we considered, $Q \sim 0.8$, indicating that the response curve is strongly sublinear. $D_{63\%}$ is the dose at which the OSL intensity is 63%, or more precisely $1 - 1/e$, of the saturated intensity. $D_{63\%}$ ranged from a low of 180 for one of the coarse (63–90 μm) grains to a high of 820 Gy for one of the fine (4–11 μm) grain samples. c has a value close to one and adjusts for a bias in the SAR procedure.

When there is a balance between recombination and trapping, $A_n = A_m$ (or $Q = 0$), the phenomenological model yields a saturating exponential which is close to linear at low doses and sublinear as saturation is approached. The experimental data, however, shows strong sublinearity even at low doses and this is consistent with the phenomenological model when recombination is strong: $A_m \gg A_n$. While combining two saturating exponentials can provide stronger sublinearity at low dose, the excellent fit, at least for some samples, of the phenomenological model to the experimental data, despite having fewer adjustable constants than the DSE, indicates that the analytical form from the phenomenological model may be a better starting point.

The difference between the dose response curves of fine and coarse grains can be interpreted within the phenomenological model as a change in the number of fast–OSL traps per unit volume. The observed change in trap concentrations is consistent with these traps being interface (or surface) traps, rather than volume traps, and hence that their number per unit volume scales with interface area per unit volume. The scaling with grain size is consistent with the interfaces having a fractal dimension of $D_F = 2.5$, which is midway between perfectly smooth ($D_F = 2$) and very rough ($D_F \rightarrow 3$).

We tested a model that assumed both the fast–OSL trap and deep trap were surface traps (Sec. (3.3)) and also the three possible cases in which one or both of the traps were volume traps (Sec. (3.4)). The model assuming both

were surface traps yielded a superior fit to the experimental dose response data and this is consistent with both traps being surface traps.

In this work, the larger saturation dose for fine grains versus coarse grains is explained by the scaling of surface trap versus volume trap concentrations. There may be other explanations for the larger concentration of the fast-OSL trap in fine grains. For example, there is evidence that differences in impurity concentrations in quartz can affect mechanical measures of strength such as hardness. (Nadeau, 1970; Evans, 1984) The grinding process that results in the creation of grains of various sizes will be influenced by differences in various mechanical properties including hardness. It may turn out that finer grains are more likely to be formed from sections of source material that have higher concentrations of defects that are associated with the fast-OSL or deep traps. If so, this would provide an alternative explanation of why finer grains have higher concentrations of N or N_D than coarser grains. Despite this different mechanism for explaining the correlation of trap concentrations to grain size, the mathematical approach presented in this work would otherwise remain largely unchanged.

While the empirical fit between the phenomenological model and experimental data is excellent for the samples investigated, there are two limitations to bear in mind. The first is that there are other samples, presumably with different concentrations of different traps and centers than the ones studied here, that do not fit this model. The second is that we are only matching dose response curves and there are likely multiple different models that can produce the same curves with different physical interpretations. Thus, the physical interpretation provided by the model here is inherently tentative.

Acknowledgements

ATG is funded by the European Research Council (ERC, PROGRESS, 101043356). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Council. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Appendix A. Derivation

We will develop a solution to the system of equations Eq. (4) through Eq. (8). The first step is to observe that the lifetimes of free electron and free holes, often measured in microseconds, is generally quite short compared to the irradiation time which can be minutes in a lab or much longer in the field. It follows that:

$$\frac{dn_c}{dt} \ll [A_n(N - n) + A_m m] n_c \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{dn_v}{dt} \ll B(M - m)n_v \quad (\text{A.1})$$

This leads to the quasi-steady approximation which allows Eq. (6) and Eq. (8) to be simplified to:

$$n_c = \frac{X}{A_n(N - n) + A_m m} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

$$n_v = \frac{X}{B(M - m)} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

When the free lifetimes of free electrons and free holes are short, the populations n_c and n_v become small. Consequently, conservation of charge which in general is $n_1 + n_D + n_c = m + n_v$ simplifies to $n_1 + n_D = m$. With the assumption that the deep trap is filled during the large geological dose, $n_D = N_D$, the governing equations Eq. (4) and Eq. (7) now simplify to:

$$\frac{dn}{dt} = \frac{A_n(N - n)}{A_n(N - n) + A_m m} X \quad (\text{A.4})$$

$$m = n + N_D \quad (\text{A.5})$$

where $A_n(N - n)/(A_n(N - n) + A_m m)$ has the physical meaning of being the fraction of free electrons which are captured by the trap N as opposed to recombining with center M . Eq. (A.4) and Eq. (A.5) can be immediately integrated to find:

$$D = \frac{W}{\rho} \left[\left(1 - \frac{A_m}{A_n}\right) n - \frac{A_m}{A_n} (N + N_D) \ln \left(1 - \frac{n}{N}\right) \right] \quad (\text{A.6})$$

where D is defined by Eq. (1). Rearranging Eq. (A.6), we have:

$$D = - \frac{W}{\rho} \frac{A_m}{A_n} (N + N_D) \left[\ln \left(1 - \frac{n}{N}\right) + Q \frac{n}{N} \right] \quad (\text{A.7})$$

where Q is defined by:

$$Q \equiv \left(1 - \frac{A_n}{A_m}\right) \frac{N}{N + N_D} \quad (\text{A.8})$$

In formulas for a single-saturating-exponential (SSE), it is typical to define a characteristic dose at which the OSL intensity is $1 - 1/e \approx 0.63$ of the peak. Let us find the corresponding characteristic dose for this theory. We substitute $n/N = 1 - 1/e$ into Eq. (A.7) to find:

$$D_{63\%} = \frac{W}{\rho} \frac{A_m}{A_n} (N + N_D) \left[1 + \frac{e-1}{e} Q\right] \quad (\text{A.9})$$

Using Eq. (A.9), Eq. (A.7) can be rewritten as:

$$D = D_{63\%} \frac{-\ln\left(1 - \frac{n}{N}\right) - Q \frac{n}{N}}{1 + \frac{e-1}{e} Q} \quad (\text{A.10})$$

For the special case of $Q = 0$, Eq. (A.10) can be easily solved for n , yielding a simple saturating exponential form:

$$n = N \left[1 - \exp\left(-\frac{D}{D_{63\%}}\right)\right] \quad (\text{A.11})$$

This again verifies that the parameter $D_{63\%}$ here is the same as the characteristic dose as typically used in SSE formulas.

To solve for nonzero Q , we start by rearranging Eq. (A.10):

$$-\left(1 + \frac{e-1}{e} Q\right) \frac{D}{D_{63\%}} = \ln\left(1 - \frac{n}{N}\right) + Q \frac{n}{N} \quad (\text{A.12})$$

Take the exponential of both sides of Eq. (A.12):

$$\exp\left(-\left(1 + \frac{e-1}{e} Q\right) \frac{D}{D_{63\%}}\right) = \left(1 - \frac{n}{N}\right) \exp\left(Q \frac{n}{N}\right) \quad (\text{A.13})$$

Now, multiply both sides by $-Qe^{-Q}$ to find:

$$-Q \exp\left(-Q - \left(1 + \frac{e-1}{e} Q\right) \frac{D}{D_{63\%}}\right) = -Q \left(1 - \frac{n}{N}\right) \exp\left(-Q \left(1 - \frac{n}{N}\right)\right) \quad (\text{A.14})$$

At this point, consider the definition of the Wright Omega function:

$$x = y \exp(y) \quad \iff \quad y = \mathcal{W}(x) \quad (\text{A.15})$$

It follows that:

$$-Q \left(1 - \frac{n}{N}\right) = \mathcal{W} \left(-Q \exp \left(-Q - \left(1 + \frac{e-1}{e} Q\right) \frac{D}{D_{63\%}} \right) \right) \quad (\text{A.16})$$

Rearranging yields:

$$n = N \left[1 + \frac{1}{Q} \mathcal{W} \left(-Q \exp \left(- \left(1 - \frac{e-1}{e} Q\right) \frac{D}{D_{63\%}} - Q \right) \right) \right] \quad (\text{A.17})$$

The full solution as given in Eq. (9) in Sec. (2) is the result of combining Eq. (A.17) for $Q \neq 0$ and Eq. (A.11) for $Q = 0$. Note that, for the special case of $N_D = 0$, this solution becomes equivalent to Eq. 18 of Pagonis et al. (2020).

References

- Adamiec, G., Bluszcz, A., Bailey, R., Garcia-Talavera, M., Aug 2006. Finding model parameters: Genetic algorithms and the numerical modelling of quartz luminescence. *Radiat. Meas.* 41 (7), 897–902.
URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2006.05.005>
- Alig, R. C., Bloom, S., 1975. Electron-hole-pair creation energies in semiconductors. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 35, 1522–1525.
URL <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevLett.35.1522>
- Arshak, K., Korostynska, O., 2006. *Advanced Materials and Techniques for Radiation Dosimetry*. Artech House, Boston.
- Attix, F. H., 2004. *Introduction to Radiological Physics and Radiation Dosimetry*. John Wiley and Sons.
- Bailey, R. M., Feb 2001. Towards a general kinetic model for optically and thermally stimulated luminescence of quartz. *Radiat. Meas.* 33 (1), 17–45.
URL [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1350-4487\(00\)00100-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1350-4487(00)00100-1)
- Bailey, R. M., Jun 2004. Paper i—simulation of dose absorption in quartz over geological timescales and its implications for the precision and accuracy of optical dating. *Radiat. Meas.* 38 (3), 299–310.
URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2003.09.005>

- Barnett, A. M., Lees, J. E., Bassford, D. J., 2013. Temperature dependence of the average electron-hole pair creation energy in $\text{Al}_{0.8}\text{Ga}_{0.2}\text{As}$. *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 102 (18), 181119.
URL <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4804989>
- Evans, B., Jun 1984. The effect of temperature and impurity content on indentation hardness of quartz. *J. Geophys. Res. Solid Earth* 89 (B6), 4213–4222.
URL <https://doi.org/10.1029/JB089iB06p04213>
- Giordano, L., Sushko, P. V., Pacchioni, G., Shluger, A. L., Sep 2007. Electron trapping at point defects on hydroxylated silica surfaces. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 99 (13), 136801.
URL <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevLett.99.136801>
- Goetzberger, A., Klausmann, E., Schulz, M. J., Jan 1976. Interface states on semiconductor/insulator surfaces. *C R C Critical Rev. Solid State Sci.* 6 (1), 1–43.
URL <https://doi.org/10.1080/10408437608243548>
- Goldstein, B., 1965. Electron–hole pair creation in gallium phosphide by α particles. *J. Appl. Phys.* 36 (12), 3853–3856.
URL <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1713961>
- Heremans, J., Aug 1993. Solid state magnetic field sensors and applications. *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* 26 (8), 1149–1168.
URL <https://doi.org/10.1088/0022-3727/26/8/001>
- Hözl, J., Schulte, F. K., Wagner, H., 1979. *Solid Surface Physics. Vol. 85 of Springer Tracts in Modern Physics.* Springer, Berlin.
URL <https://doi.org/10.1007/BFb0048918>
- Ibach, H., 2006. *Physics of Surfaces and Interfaces.* Springer, Berlin.
URL <https://doi.org/10.1007/3-540-34710-0>
- Kijek, N., Chruścińska, A., Jul 2016. Natural and laboratory osl growth curve–verification of the basic assumption of luminescence dating. *Radiat. Meas.* 90, 233–237.
URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2016.01.024>

- Klein, C. A., 1968. Bandgap dependence and related features of radiation ionization energies in semiconductors. *J. Appl. Phys.* 39 (4), 2029–2038.
URL <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1656484>
- Lawless, J. L., Chen, R., Pagonis, V., May 2009. Sublinear dose dependence of thermoluminescence and optically stimulated luminescence prior to the approach to saturation level. *Radiat. Meas.* 44 (5), 606–610.
URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2009.03.003>
- Lawless, J. L., Chen, R., Pagonis, V., Feb 2022. Effect of radiation physics on inherent statistics of glow curves from small samples or low doses. *Radiat. Meas.* 151, 106698.
URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2021.106698>
- Lowick, S. E., Preusser, F., Wintle, A. G., Oct 2010. Investigating quartz optically stimulated luminescence dose–response curves at high doses. *Radiat. Meas.* 45 (9), 975–984.
URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2010.07.010>
- Lüth, H., 2001. *Solid Surfaces, Interfaces and Thin Films* (Springer 2001), 4th Edition. Springer.
URL <https://libgen.fun/book/index.php?md5=a6fe3aa21ec7e23700535f59c957a28c>
- Murray, A. S., Svendsen, J. I., Mangerud, J., Astakhov, V. I., Jan 2007. Testing the accuracy of quartz osl dating using a known-age eemian site on the river sula, northern russia. *Quat. Geochronol.* 2 (1), 102–109.
URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quageo.2006.04.004>
- Murray, A. S., Wintle, A. G., Aug 2003. The single aliquot regenerative dose protocol: potential for improvements in reliability. *Radiat. Meas.* 37 (4), 377–381.
URL [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1350-4487\(03\)00053-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1350-4487(03)00053-2)
- Nadeau, J. S., Oct 1970. Influence of hydrogen and alkali impurities on the high-temperature indentation hardness of natural quartz crystals. *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 53 (10), 568–570.
URL <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1151-2916.1970.tb15968.x>
- Pagonis, V., Kitis, G., Chen, R., Sep 2020. A new analytical equation for the dose response of dosimetric materials, based on the lambert w function. *J.*

- Lumin. 225, 117333.
URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jlumin.2020.117333>
- Pagonis, V., Wintle, A. G., Chen, R., Wang, X. L., Feb 2008. A theoretical model for a new dating protocol for quartz based on thermally transferred osl (tt-osl). *Radiat. Meas.* 43 (2), 704–708.
URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2008.01.025>
- Pawley, S. M., Toms, P., Armitage, S. J., Rose, J., Oct 2010. Quartz luminescence dating of anglian stage (mis 12) fluvial sediments: Comparison of sar age estimates to the terrace chronology of the middle thames valley, uk. *Quat. Geochronol.* 5 (5), 569–582.
URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1871101409001344>
- Peng, J., Wang, X., Adamiec, G., Zhao, H., Dec 2022. Critical role of the deep electron trap in explaining the inconsistency of sensitivity-corrected natural and regenerative growth curves of quartz osl at high irradiation doses. *Radiat. Meas.* 159, 106874.
URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2022.106874>
- Popovic, R. S., Baltes, H. P., Rudolf, F., 1984. An integrated silicon magnetic field sensor using the magnetodiode principle. *IEEE Transactions on Electron Devices* 31 (3), 286–291.
URL <https://doi.org/10.1109/T-ED.1984.21516>
- Ryan, R. D., 1973. Precision measurements of the ionization energy and its temperature variation in high purity silicon radiation detectors. *IEEE Transactions on Nucl. Sci.* 20 (1), 473 – 480.
- Scholze, F., Rabus, H., Ulm, G., 1998. Mean energy required to produce an electron-hole pair in silicon for photons of energies between 50 and 1500 eV. *J. Appl. Phys.* 84 (5), 2926–2939.
URL <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.368398>
- Skuja, L., Ollier, N., Kajihara, K., Jul 2020. Luminescence of non-bridging oxygen hole centers as a marker of particle irradiation of α -quartz. *Radiat. Meas.* 135, 106373.
URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2020.106373>
- Timar, A., Vandenberghe, D., Panaiotu, E. C., Panaiotu, C. G., Necula, C., Cosma, C., van den haute, P., Apr 2010. Optical dating of romanian loess

- using fine-grained quartz. *Quat. Geochronol.* 5 (2), 143–148.
URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quageo.2009.03.003>
- Timar-Gabor, A., Dec 2018. Electron spin resonance characterisation of sedimentary quartz of different grain sizes. *Radiat. Meas.* 120, 59–65.
URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2018.06.023>
- Timar-Gabor, A., Buylaert, J.-P., Guralnik, B., Trandafir-Antohei, O., Constantin, D., Anechitei-Deacu, V., Jain, M., Murray, A., Porat, N., Hao, Q., Wintle, A., 2017. On the importance of grain size in luminescence dating using quartz. *Radiat. Meas.* 106, 464–471, proceedings of the 18th International Conference on Solid State Dosimetry (SSD18), Munich, Germany, 3 – 8 July 2016.
URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1350448717300446>
- Timar-Gabor, A., Vandenberghe, D. A. G., Vasiliniuc, S., Panaoitu, C. E., Panaiotu, C. G., Dimofte, D., Cosma, C., Aug 2011. Optical dating of romanian loess: A comparison between silt-sized and sand-sized quartz. *Quat. Int.* 240 (1), 62–70.
URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.quaint.2010.10.007>
- Timar-Gabor, A., Vasiliniuc, S., Vandenberghe, D. A. G., Cosma, C., Wintle, A. G., Sep 2012. Investigations into the reliability of sar-osl equivalent doses obtained for quartz samples displaying dose response curves with more than one component. *Radiat. Meas.* 47 (9), 740–745.
URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2011.12.001>
- Wintle, A. G., Murray, A. S., Apr 2006. A review of quartz optically stimulated luminescence characteristics and their relevance in single-aliquot regeneration dating protocols. *Radiat. Meas.* 41 (4), 369–391.
URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radmeas.2005.11.001>

Supplement

Table of Contents

1	Sample Python Code to Fit SAR–OSL Data to OTORX Model.....	2
2	Additional Figures	5

1. Sample Python Code to Fit SAR-OSL Data to OTORX Model

```
#!/usr/bin/python3
"""Perform least squares fit of OSL-SAR dose, luminescence data to OTORX model.

If this code is run, as is, it will output a fit to sample data.
To run this on your own data, you need to modify three lines.  Toward the end
of the file, make these changes:
    1. Set 'TEST_DOSE' to the correct dose for your experiment
    2. Set 'DOSE' to the array of laboratory doses for your data
    3. Set 'LxTx' to the array of luminescence values for laboratory doses
       normalized by luminescence at the test dose

Reference:
Lawless & Timar-Gabor, "A new analytical model to fit both fine and
coarse grained quartz luminescence dose response curves," Radiation
Measurements

This code requires Python with the Numpy and Scipy packages installed.
"""

### Import required packages ###

import numpy as np
from scipy.special import lambertw as W
from scipy.optimize import curve_fit

### Define Functions ###

_ffmt = lambda vars: ' '.join(f'{x:.3g}' for x in vars) # pretty-print a 1-D array

def nN2D(nN, Q, D63):
    """Return dose given n/N, Q, & D63.

    See Lawless & Timar-Gabor Eq 9

    >>> _ffmt(nN2D(nN=1-np.exp(-1), Q=np.array((0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8)), D63=np.array((1, 10, 100, 1000))))
    '1 10 100 1e+03'
    >>> _ffmt(nN2D(nN=0.5, Q=np.array((0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8)), D63=np.array((1, 10, 100, 1000))))
    '0.648 6.33 61.5 593'
    """
    return D63 * ((-np.log(1-nN) - Q*nN)/(1 - Q*(1-np.exp(-1))))

def D2nN(D, Q, D63):
    """Return n/N given dose D and parameters Q & D63.

    See Lawless & Timar-Gabor Equations 9 & 10

    Parameters
    -----
    D : number or array of numbers
        Dose (same units as D63)
    Q : number or array of numbers
```

```

    Q = (1 - An/Am)(N/(N+ND))
D63 : number or array of numbers
    Characteristic dose (in same units as D) when n/N=1- 1/e

Returns
-----
r : three numbers
    Q, D63, c

Examples
-----
>>> _ffmt(D2nN(1, Q=np.array((-10, -3, 0.1, 1)), D63=1))
'0.632 0.632 0.632 0.632'
"""
D = np.asarray(D)
if np.all(abs(Q) < 1e-6):
    r = 1 - np.exp(-D/D63)
elif np.any(abs(Q) < 1e-6):
    raise ValueError(f'Unsupported of zero and nonzero Q: Q={Q}')
else:
    w = W(-Q * np.exp(-Q-(1.-Q*(1.-1./np.exp(1)))*D/D63))
    assert np.allclose(w.imag, 0)
    r = 1 + w.real/Q
return r

# fn_otorx is a function which takes dose & log10 of the 3 parameters as arguments and returns n/N
fn_otorx = lambda D, logQ, logD63, logc: D2nN(D, 10**logQ, 10**logD63) * 10**logc / D2nN(TEST_DOSE, 10**logQ, 10**logD63)

def xy2otorxfit(dose, LxTx, pguess=None, sigma=None):
    """Return best fit parameters (Q, D63, c) given dose & intensity data.

Parameters
-----
dose : array of numbers
    Laboratory dose
LxTx : array of numbers
    Luminescence at laboratory dose divided by luminescence for test dose
pguess : None or three numbers
    Leave this as None and the code will select a reasonable first guess
    for the nonlinear fit
    If that is not working for you, supply a first guess for (Q, D63, c)
sigma : None or array of numbers
    Weighting factors used by SciPy's curve_fit function.
    If you have error estimates for each data point in LxTx, you may enter that here.
    If sigma=1, then the absolute errors in luminescence will be minimized.
    If sigma is None or LxTx, then fractional errors will be minimized.

Returns
-----
r : three numbers
    (Q, D63, c)
"""
dose = np.asarray(dose)

```

```

LxTx = np.asarray(LxTx)
if sigma is None:
    sigma = LxTx # minimize relative errors.
if pguess is None:
    pguess = 0.9, np.max(dose), 1
pguess = np.asarray(pguess)
logpguess = np.log10(pguess)
log_r, unused_cov = curve_fit(fn_otorx, dose, LxTx, p0=logpguess, sigma=sigma)
r = 10**log_r
return r # r = (Q, D63, c)

### Define data, fit to OTORX model, and display results ###

# Replace the next three lines with your actual data:
TEST_DOSE = 17
DOSE = (17, 47, 94, 201, 402, 804, 1.07e+03, 1.68e+03, 3.35e+03, 5.36e+03, 6.7e+03, 8.04e+03,
        1e+04, 47, 94, 3.35e+03, 5.36e+03)
LxTx = (1.09, 2.3, 3.67, 5.63, 8.09, 10.3, 11.4, 13, 14.8, 15.8, 16.9, 17, 17.1, 2.26, 3.65,
        15.6, 15.9)

assert len(DOSE) == len(LxTx) # There must be one LxTx value for each dose

# Perform fit
Q, D63, c = xy2otorxfit(DOSE, LxTx)
print(f'Best fit: {Q:.3g} {D63:.3g} {c:.3g}\n')

# Display results
fit = c * D2nN(DOSE, Q, D63) / D2nN(TEST_DOSE, Q, D63)
print('%10s %10s %10s' % ('Dose', 'Lx/Tx', 'Best Fit'))
for row in zip(DOSE, LxTx, fit):
    print('%10.0f %10.2f %10.2f' % tuple(row))

```

2. Additional Figures

Figure S.1: The data for sample MV10, as used in Figure 3 of the text, is replotted here with different scales. In order to show saturation clearly, the x -axis scale has been extended to 10⁵ Gy. Also, to highlight saturation, the intensity on the y -axis is normalized by the saturation intensity from the fit of the data to the OTORX model. The experimental data are shown with error bars of ± 1 standard deviation. For an alternate view of the fit quality, see Fig. S.6 in this supplement.

Figure S.2: This plot is in the style of Fig. S.1 but is done for sample CST inf. Data for both fine and coarse grain samples are shown.

Figure S.3: This plot is in the style of Fig. S.1 but is done for sample M#6#. Data for both fine and coarse grain samples are shown.

Figure S.4: This plot is in the style of Fig. S.1 but is done for sample MST 19. Data for both fine and coarse grain samples are shown.

Figure S.5: This plot is in the style of Fig. S.1 but is done for sample XF 153 A. Data for both fine and coarse grain samples are shown.

Figure S.6: In the manuscript, Figure 3 showed experimental SAR-OSL intensity for sample MV10 and two analytical fits to that data. This graph plots residuals of these two fits normalised by the estimated standard deviation, σ , at each data point of the experimental data. The gray box highlights the region in which the errors are within $\pm 2\sigma$ of the experimental value. The open diamonds are for the OTOX fit. The open triangles are for the double-saturating-exponential (DSE) fit. Both fits do well at high dose where the intensity approaches saturation. The OTOX fit is more accurate at low dose.